

AN ENSEMBLE LEARNING BASED PREDICTION ANALYTICS FRAMEWORK FOR HEALTHCARE

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Abstract

Ensemble learning helps to develop multiple learners and combine the results of them to improve the accuracy of prediction. As the ensemble learning methods help boost the weak learners, thus leads to have multiple learners help to improve the learning process. Even though the cost associated with ensemble learning is higher, as per 'No Free Lunch' theorem, as the effectiveness and efficiency in terms of learning and prediction is higher, this cost increase can be compromised. In this research work, the application of ensemble learning is extended in predicting the diseases well before based on the symptoms gathered from the patients. Such prediction helps in improving the efficiency of the diagnostics by prioritizing with high level of accuracy. Further, this work also compares the results of existing techniques and the proposed technique and shows that, the proposed work proves to be efficient in terms of prediction accuracy.

Keywords: Ensemble Learning, Healthcare, Prediction Analytics, Machine Learning Models, Accuracy

1. INTRODUCTION

Healthcare is the most important and crucial area of research for which several innovations have been taken place. In real time healthcare applications, the predictions are essential to provide proper decisions and recommendations in order to save the human life. It is of paramount importance in predicting the patient's health status based on the past and the current observations. Especially, when it is coming on to predictive analytics for healthcare, the machine learning algorithms play a vital role in analysing the existing patterns of patients and providing suggestions and recommendations.

To achieve this, the proposed research work focuses on the application of ensemble learning algorithm which combines the best characteristics of two or more ML classifiers along with improvement heuristics in getting the improved solution in the healthcare domain.

For the purpose of accomplishing this, the framework that has been proposed has generated the consistent hypothesis version space. This space is based on the data that has been gathered from the real-time observation of a patient. It is necessary to place their symptoms into the appropriate group in accordance with hypothesis H in order to accomplish this goal. This hypothesis function is a representation of the mapping of new input data, which may be a new symptom or an updated version of an existing symptom that is being considered, to the appropriate target labels, classes, or categories. The purpose of this hypothesis H is to determine whether or not it is possible to resemble the unknown symptom, which could be a new symptom or a changed symptom, as closely as possible in order to minimize the number of generalization mistakes. Because of this, real-time healthcare requires such a categorization in order to carry out such predictions. This ensures that none of the key symptoms are missed in the process of disease detection.

Due to the fact that it utilized both supervised and unsupervised learning methods, this research endeavor utilized the ensemble learning technique. In the process of supervised learning, the hypothesis H is supervised based on the output labels that are known to be either "critical" or "non-critical" based on the samples of training data. In the context of unsupervised learning, the generation of hypothesis H occurs without any supervision being provided because there are no known output data samples accessible from the training data base. The purpose of having a correct hypothesis H is to ensure that it functions more effectively when applied to data that is already unknown.

In ensemble learning or ensemble model, the prediction of different models is combined to make a final prediction model. Here, it is achieved by means of averaging and voting which is together called as 'average voting' which is found to be better than independent learning algorithms.

The viable reasons of ensemble learning produces better results are: the application of statistical methods, computational and representation learning algorithms, calculation of bias-variance decomposition method and strength-correlation methods.

Generally, in deep learning, the features in the upper layer are generated based on the previous set of layer or layers. Deep learning has application areas in pattern matching, object identification, video analytics etc. Here, this is extended in this research work to apply the effectiveness of ensemble learning or ensemble model to predict the critical symptoms.

In this work, a novel unified framework to predict the disease based on the critical symptoms using ensemble model or ensemble learning is applied especially in healthcare domain to provide high accuracy to reduce human mortality. This research work further analyzes the existing works which applied ensemble learning and deep learning for problem domains such as classification, regression and clustering.

1.1 Research Objectives

The objectives of the proposed work are three fold: (i) To develop an unified framework for healthcare analytics using Ensemble learning (ii) To evaluate the ML algorithms and selecting the better ones for Ensemble Learning (iii) To assess the trustworthiness of the proposed ensemble classifier using various metrics and measures.

2. Materials and methods

There are some existing works on ensemble learning carried out by several researchers. Some of them are provided here as part of the literature.

A review of the utilization of ensemble learning models for the purposes of classifying, selecting, and composing web services was presented by Hasnain et al. [1]. Their strategy sought to evaluate classifiers such as Naive Bayes, Support Vector Machine, and others in order to identify performance aspects of web services based on classification results. This research offered some understanding regarding the utilization of Naïve Bayes and SVM classifiers in the work that was proposed.

In their study, Smirani et al. [2] introduced a novel approach called Stacked Generalization for Failure Prediction (SGFP) to assess and enhance the academic performance of students. The authors have integrated three ensemble learning classifiers—eXtreme Gradient Boosting Machine (XGB), Random Forest (RF), and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LGBM)—using a Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) in their proposed method. Full Grade Center and Blackboard Learning Management System datasets were utilized. It is determined, based on their outcomes, that the performance of the combined technique was superior to that of the individual classifiers. Consequently, this research advances to the implementation of ensemble learning, which enhances performance by combining the most advantageous attributes of individual classifiers.

Ganaiea et al. [3] have completed a review of deep ensemble models and provided researchers with a summary of these techniques. Furthermore, the utilization of deep ensemble models across various domains of application has been deliberated. This work influenced the proposed work's implementation of ensemble learning on account of its summary and application of ensemble techniques.

Saxena et al. [4] have endeavored to develop a predictive method that can identify unintentional falls among humans based on their health parameters. The issue of syncope in humans has been investigated in order to prevent falls through the prediction of abnormal changes in health parameters such as blood pressure, blood sugar, pulse rate, and so forth. They utilized a variety of classification algorithms and employed the cross-validation technique to verify the outcomes. The results of their study suggest that the ensemble technique they proposed outperforms the KNN algorithm. The proposed research examined this body of work and determined that the cross-validation method was utilized to validate the results in healthcare analytics.

Su et al. [5] have presented a solution to the difficulty associated with the implementation of machine learning algorithms, which results in performance fluctuations for the model. For dynamically evolving diagnostic task scenarios, the authors have proposed a combined Deep Ensemble Model and tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) as well as an adaptive deep ensemble learning method (TPE-DEM). Using publicly available datasets from UCI, they have demonstrated that their model outperforms competing baseline models. By utilizing publicly accessible datasets, this research was able to apply a variety of ML classifiers to the available data for comparative analysis.

Gupta et al. [6] have introduced an innovative ensemble technique known as the Stacking Ensemble-based intelligent machine learning model, which aims to forecast the occurrence of complications in patients inflicted with COVID-19 subsequent to the infection. To forecast cardiac diseases subsequent to the COVID-19 pandemic, they have put forth a stacking ensemble model utilizing deep neural networks and binary classifiers. They have validated their model and determined that, in terms of predicting problems that may arise after COVID-19, their proposed model outperforms individual models. In the domain of healthcare, this activity has contributed to our proposed research. Additionally, the proposed ensemble-based machine learning model for the COVID-19 dataset identified the utilization of layering in comparison to other ensemble learning methods.

In their study, Fayaz et al. [7] present an ensemble machine learning model designed to identify and categorize products from e-commerce applications as spam or nonspam. They utilized a combination of MLP, KNN, and Random Forest predictions to determine whether a product review was fraud or not. In terms of classification accuracy, their findings indicate that the proposed ensemble model outperformed the individual classifiers and boosting approaches. This effort contributed to a greater understanding of how the ensemble learning algorithm could be implemented in the proposed work.

A review of the most recent research proceedings in the field of ensemble learning was conducted by Dong et al. [8]. It is evident from their research that ensemble learning involves the extraction of features through a multitude of transformations. Furthermore, the methodologies utilized in ensemble learning have

been categorized according to their distinct attributes. They detailed the difficulties and future research directions associated with each ensemble learning approach in their paper.

Singh and Pal [9] implemented various machine learning models, including Decision Tree (DT), Naïve Bayesian (NB), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Extra Tree (ET), on an individual basis. Subsequently, they constructed a model that amalgamates the outcomes of each individual base learner through the utilization of Boosting and Bagging ensemble methods. They demonstrated, through a comparison of outcomes, that the packaging method yielded superior results in comparison to the alternatives. They conducted this investigation using only bagging and boosting techniques and determined that bagging is the more effective method. In order to verify this, the proposed research utilized boosting, bundling, and stacking, and determined that stacking produced superior results.

Mienye et al. [10] put forth an enhanced machine learning approach for the purpose of ascertaining the risk of cardiac disease. By randomly dividing the dataset into smaller subsets and applying the classification and regression tree (CART) model to create a weighted aging classifier ensemble, they were able to achieve optimal performance. The integration of methodologies, such as ensemble classifiers, enabled the implementation of this combined technique in the proposed study.

Krawczyk et al. [11] covered the classification and regression of data streams in ensemble learning in their survey paper. In contrast to conventional data mining techniques, ensemble learning algorithms have been found to necessitate greater computational resources for the processing of data streams. A thorough examination of the shortcomings of current ensemble methods has been undertaken, along with a discourse on sophisticated learning techniques including active and semi-supervised learning, novelty detection, imbalanced data streams, and complex data representations, among others. This paper presented compelling evidence regarding the utilization of ensemble techniques for classification problems, which forms the foundation of this research endeavor.

Webb and Zeng [12] have provided evidence that the prediction accuracy of boosting and bagging decision tree algorithms is superior to that of base learning algorithms. They have also demonstrated the enhanced outcomes that can be achieved through the integration of basic ensemble methodologies. The authors of the paper conducted an analysis of the hypothesis that combined approaches lead to an improvement in accuracy. Additionally, they have devised and demonstrated three multi-strategy ensemble learning methods, which increase accuracy as a result of the combined approach. Due to the enhanced accuracy achieved through the combined approach, the combined approach was also implemented in ensemble learning in the proposed work.

The study [13] examined space-efficient and time-efficient ensemble learners for a platform for online learning with extremely limited resources. The learning algorithms suggested in this study have implemented a framework for boosting through filtering and a particular boosting algorithm. Ensembles of online decision trees were trained utilizing the ID4 online-based decision tree algorithm. The methods implemented for the branch prediction domain and three online machine learning benchmark problems have been evaluated at last. The results of their study demonstrated that the performance of individual decision trees was enhanced by the ID4 with additional features, and that it achieved even greater performance in ensembles of trees. Additionally, the accuracy of ensembles generated using boosting-style ensemble algorithms is enhanced as ensemble size increases. Nevertheless, it has been determined that the efficacy of the bagging algorithm was inferior to that of the boosting algorithm.

Krogh and Sollich [14] have investigated the learning norm that the ensemble learning-using students' community adheres to. They discovered that it is preferable to use students in the underregularized categories, which overfit the trained data, for large ensembles. In order to achieve optimal generalization performance, care is taken in the selection of the students' training sets. In the case of smaller ensembles, the efficacy of the ensemble is enhanced through the optimization of ensemble weights.

Chandra and Yao (2015) have identified two metrics that comprise the ensemble: diversity and accuracy of the neural networks. An algorithm has been suggested which generates an ensemble and proceeds to locate the optimal point on the curve fit in terms of diversity-accuracy. It is expressed as a problem with multiple objectives.

The authors of a research paper [16] conducted a comparative analysis of the performance evaluation of ensemble methods for sentimental analysis, including bagging, boosting, and random subspace. The aforementioned techniques are implemented utilizing SVM, Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree, K-Nearest Neighbor, and Maximum Entropy. The findings of their study suggested that the ensemble classifiers exhibited superior performance. Moreover, ensemble learning is a superior approach for applications based on sentimental classification, as demonstrated by the results indicating that Random Space offered superior performance.

In financial applications, an examination of the different learning methodologies is undertaken with regard to credit assessment [17]. Based on the findings, ensemble methods including stacking, bagging, and bolstering were applied to the different learners. Logistic Regression Analysis, Decision Tree, and SVM

indicate that the performance of the individual learners has been substantially enhanced by the ensemble methods applied to these learners.

Rahayu et al. [18] put forth ten single machine learning models and two ensemble learning models in order to assess the ensemble model's performance. This study presents an ensemble method for predicting the bankruptcy of Indonesian public companies and evaluates its efficacy in comparison to alternative singular machine learning approaches. Ensemble learning exhibits superior and more consistent performance in comparison to individual models, with AdaBoost demonstrating the highest performance. It does not appear that an imbalance in the data affects the results; however, this may warrant additional investigation in future research.

The model proposed by Fitriyani et al. [19] utilized ANN, SVM, and DT for training data, followed by the ensemble method for output prediction. This paper proposes a disease prediction model (DPM) that integrates iForest, SMOTE-Tomek, and ensemble learning for type 2 diabetes and hypertension. By detecting imbalanced and outlier-filled data and improving accuracy, the DPM achieves high rates of accuracy when evaluated on a variety of datasets. A mobile application is also integrated to enable real-time monitoring and diagnosis.

In their study, Qummar et al. [20] proposed an ensemble classifier that utilizes consensus vote for the purpose of classification. In order to address the limitations of individual classifiers, ensemble classifiers exhibit superior performance. By employing ensemble learning algorithms based on majority voting and texture attributes extracted from the gray level co-occurrence matrix, this study introduces a novel methodology for identifying diabetic retinopathy in color fundus images. The accuracy is improved by employing a correlation matrix to select relevant features and integrating the predictions of multiple base classifiers. The proposed method surpasses all alternative standalone classifier algorithms in terms of accuracy, particularity, and receptivity. Since the current system exclusively utilizes hard majority voting, it is not impossible to expand this study to include soft majority voting. Our proposed framework incorporates this feature.

An investigation was conducted by Mahajan et al. [21] into the precision of various ensemble techniques, including aggregating, stacking, voting, and boosting. Experiments were conducted on various maladies that impact critical organs, including the kidney, liver, skin, heart, and diabetes. Stacking yielded the highest degree of accuracy among the three ensemble methods, according to their findings. They also demonstrated that the performance accuracy of ensemble techniques differs according to the category of disease dataset. This study yielded valuable insights regarding the considerable variation in performance levels among the various ensemble learning techniques.

Nguyen et al. [22] enhanced the performance of a number of weak classifiers and ensured their stability by employing ensemble technique. The authors implemented gradient deep learning boosting, deep aggregation learning, deep-sacked generalization ensemble learning, and deep boosting and demonstrated that the proposed methods produced more reliable results than the ML and DL algorithms that are typically used for classification. After comparing the F1 scores of each technique, they came to the conclusion that the performance of the proposed work is consistent and dependable.

Namamula et al. [23] have successfully combined two machine learning algorithms, specifically 'Edge Detection Instance Preference' and 'XG Boost', in order to enhance the accuracy of each algorithm when used in isolation. The approach has been evaluated on four distinct datasets, and the authors assert that the outcomes are encouraging.

Mung and Phyu [24] have both implemented and evaluated the functionality of a variety of ML algorithms. The ML algorithms were subsequently combined to produce an ensemble learning classifier, which was designed to enhance the classifier's accuracy. Additionally, fuzzy voting, an effective component of the ensemble learning method, has been implemented. In addition, the outcome was highly accurate.

Ganie and Malik [25] have devised a framework for ensemble learning capable of predicting type II diabetes. An exploratory data analysis technique was implemented, incorporating synthetic minority oversampling and k-fold cross validation, in order to enhance the quality, class balance, and validation, respectively. The findings of their research demonstrated that the bagging technique yielded favorable outcomes for the decision tree-based base classifier.

Based on the aforementioned literature reviews, it has been determined that when using multiple ML classifiers for real-time domains, the outcomes were superior to those obtained with the use of individual ML classifiers. As a result, the literature review concludes that ensemble learning is the most suitable alternative even in the healthcare domain, which also requires a high degree of precision.

The metric evaluation of each of these existing approaches assisted the present work in identifying the superior model for the medical domain by employing comparable metrics (e.g., accuracy, precision, recall, F1 Score).

The research gaps are also identified through this literature survey. Some of the works have not at all applied stacking even though this method in ensemble learning provided improved metric values. Hence, this

work has extensively applied all the predominant ML classifiers and also experimented bagging, boosting and stacking in ensemble learning.

3. METHOD

3.1 Proposed Framework

Figure 1 – Proposed Framework on the application of Ensemble Learning

This research work has focused on the application of ensemble learning with soft voting technique by combining it with the best learner identified from the implementation based on its resultant accuracy and F1 Score.

The proposed framework as shown in Figure 1, starts with the sample dataset taken from already proven repositories. Then, the dataset is preprocessed and then based on the application of various classifiers, the metrics such as accuracy, precision, F1 Score, and Recall are collected.

Further, the proposed Ensemble classifier is applied by combining the best classifiers taken from the implementation based on their accuracy and F1 Score and then soft voting classifier is applied on it to get the better result. By varying the parameters and the corresponding values, the performance of the proposed work is compared with the existing classifiers.

Finally the result analysis and comparative study are provided as the outcome to the researchers to derive the application of ensemble learning in any healthcare data for the prediction analytics. It has the following components. It is identified that, the ensemble classifier provided a better accuracy of 91.02%.

Data Description

This research study focuses on utilizing a diabetic dataset for experimenting purposes. The dataset consists of 9 columns, including one output column that indicates whether an individual has a positive or negative diagnosis for diabetes. The dataset consists of 768 rows, with 500 rows representing non-diabetic patients and the remaining 268 rows representing diabetes patients. The dataset consists of nine feature columns, including pregnant month, glucose level, plasma level, blood pressure, triceps skin fold thickness, insulin amount, BMI, pedigree function, and age of patients. Additionally, there is one goal column which has values of either 0 or 1. This dataset has been sourced from Kaggle for the purpose of experimenting.

Data preprocessing

Data pre-processing is a crucial stage in which data is transformed into a practical and effective format to be inputted into the machine learning algorithm. Data normalization is the initial approach employed for data pre-processing. This method is employed to carry out a linear transformation of data. It is referred to as Min-max normalization, which ensures that all attribute values fall inside the range of [0, 1]. Subsequently, the employed pre-processing approach is label encoding. This technique is utilized to assess the dependent variable, specifically if an individual has diabetes or not. All the string values in the output variable are substituted with either 0 or 1 to determine the output class. The dataset contained numerous missing values for different categories. Specifically, the pregnancy attribute had 111 missing values, the insulin attribute had 374 missing values, and the skin thickness attribute had 227 missing values. The missing values were imputed using the median value for a certain attribute. This data-preprocessing approach is often referred to as median replacement.

Model architecture

Figure 2 – Ensemble Learning based Prediction Analytics

As shown in Figure 2, the dataset is divided into 'n' bags and are sent to different classifiers at the same time. The outcome of these classifiers are fed into the ensemble model which then based on the averaging technique provides the final prediction result.

In ensemble learning, multiple individual learners (or models) are combined to produce a more accurate prediction. Due to high variance or high bias, a single model, also known as a base or weak learner, may not fare well on its own. Aggregating weak learners, however, can create a strong learner by reducing bias or variance and improving overall model performance.

In order to improve generalization to new datasets, ensemble methods are used to counteract the effects of over fitting and under fitting on individual algorithms in the model.

It is crucial to note that decision trees are not the sole modeling strategy that employs ensemble learning to identify the optimal point within the bias-variance tradeoff, as they might exhibit either high variance or high bias.

Ensemble learning methods, such as "bagging" or "bootstrap aggregation," are commonly used to mitigate the impact of noise in intricate datasets.

Bagging is a technique that includes randomly selecting a subset of a training set, allowing for the possibility of selecting the same data points numerous times due to replacement. It can be expressed as,

- Sample m datasets D_1, D_m are taken with replacement.
- For each D_j train a classifier h_j .

The final classifier is,

$$h(x) = 1/m \sum_{j=1}^m h_j(x) \quad (1)$$

Mathematically, it is represented as,

$$\widehat{f}_{bag} = \widehat{f}_1(X) + \widehat{f}_2(X) + \dots + \widehat{f}_b(X) \tag{2}$$

These models, which lack reliability, are trained individually using several generated data samples. Depending on the specific job, such as regression or classification, the average or majority of these predictions are used to provide a more accurate estimate. Bagging trains weak learners in parallel, while boosting trains them sequentially. Bagging strategies are most effective for weak learners that have large volatility and low bias, but boosting approaches can be advantageous for learners with low variance and high bias. This research work utilizes the soft voting strategy to achieve efficient and optimized results.

Soft voting is a method in which we make predictions about the class labels by using the predicted probability p for the classifier. This method is only suggested in situations when the classifiers have been properly and accurately calibrated.

$$y = \underset{i}{\operatorname{argmax}} \sum_{j=1}^n (l_m w_j p_{ij}) \tag{3}$$

The equation Eq.(3) represents the weight that can be assigned to the j th classifier from the set of possible weights.

The application of a soft voting classifier is included in this proposed work. For the goal of classification, the ensemble voting classifier is utilized to combine machine learning classifiers that are conceptually similar to one another or different from one another. This is done for the purpose of using either the majority vote or the plurality vote. In most cases, the researchers favor "hard voting" as the voting method. Nevertheless, the purpose of this research job was to investigate the usefulness of a soft vote classifier. This is because all of the classifiers that we are going to utilize have been properly calibrated before the event itself.

For the purpose of further processing, the suggested work has a well-calibrated classifier that has a high level of accuracy and an F1 Score. This is accomplished by applying the tailored implementation of each machine learning classifier on the dataset that was chosen.

Python packages such as scikit-learn make it easy to combine the outcomes of many base learners or estimators, which ultimately results in improved overall model performance.

Problem Statement

The problem here is to improve the low level of accuracy achieved by the existing ML algorithms when used on healthcare datasets, Hence, it is essential to propose a better ML algorithm to get high accuracy.

As each and everyday amount of data generated is very huge the accuracy level currently achieved by the algorithms aren't enough to rely on them completely.

There needs to be an improvement in the accuracy level to predict some crucial real world problems such as diabetes kinds of diseases in healthcare Hence, this research work takes this as the problem to solve and to arrive at a common framework to perform prediction analytics with high level of accuracy.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Case Study Implemetation

The dataset is taken from Kaggle as it is a repository used by researchers to get a comparative analysis. Diabetes dataset [26] is taken from it for the analysis. The snapshot of the dataset taken for analytics is given in table 1.

Table 1 – Sample Dataset for Healthcare Analytics

Pregnancies	Glucose	BloodPressure	SkinThickness	Insulin	BMI	DiabetesPedigreeFunction	Age	Outcome
6	148	72	35	0	33.6	0.627	50	1
1	85	66	29	0	26.6	0.351	31	0
8	183	64	0	0	23.3	0.672	32	1
1	89	66	23	94	28.1	0.167	21	0
0	137	40	35	168	43.1	2.288	33	1
5	116	74	0	0	25.6	0.201	30	0
.....								

Several other kinds of classifiers and repressors are probably going to be included in the algorithms that were utilized in the research work that was just mentioned, which concerned the application of ensemble learning in the health care and financial sectors. Some examples of these are decision tree classifiers, logistic regression classifiers, support vector machines, naive Bayes classifiers, and random forest classifiers. Other examples are random forest classifiers.

The algorithms that are selected will be determined by the characteristics of the data that is being examined

as well as the particular research objectives of the study. It is also possible that the study will make use of a variety of ensemble approaches, such as boosting, bagging, and voting, in order to aggregate the predictions of these distinct models in order to enhance the overall accuracy of the system.

The features analysis of the dataset that was provided is displayed in Figure 3. On the basis of the heat map that was produced for the dataset in question, which displays the correlation analysis of the degree to which the variables in the dataset are significant. As a result of its ability to assist in locating the characteristics that have a more direct influence on the outcome, it is simpler to identify the essential characteristics for training and testing.

Features Analysis

Figure 3 – Feature analysis of the given dataset

Figure 4 – Heat map of the features

The below sections show the application of different classifiers and the corresponding results on the above dataset.

4.1 Random Forest Classifier:

One type of ensemble learning technique that can be used to solve classification and regression issues is called Random Forest. It consists of a series of decision trees, each of which is trained on a different subset of the data that was used for training.

The ultimate forecasts are arrived at by taking the average of the forecasts provided by each tree. For the purpose of training the random forest classifier, the following formula is utilized:

$$\hat{y} = 1/m \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^m W_j(x_i, x')y_j \tag{4}$$

$$\text{Gini Index} = 1 - \sum_{j=1}^m P_j^2 \tag{5}$$

$$\text{Information Gain} = \text{Entropy}(S) - [(\text{Weighted Avg}) * \text{Entropy}(\text{each feature})] \tag{6}$$

In order to determine the metric values, the Random Forest classifier is applied to the dataset, and the metric values are obtained based on the performance of this algorithm for the real-time dataset. This is plotted in the same manner as seen in figure 5.

Figure 5 – Results of Random Forest Classifier

4.2 Gradient Boosting Classifier:

One of the ensemble learning methods that can be used to solve classification and regression issues is called Gradient Boosting. The term refers to a collection of decision trees, each of which is taught to rectify the errors that were made by the tree that came before it.

In order to arrive at the ultimate projections, the predictions of each tree are added together. The following formula is utilized in the training process of the gradient boosting classifier:

$$y(\text{pred}) = y_1 + (\text{eta} * r_1) + (\text{eta} * r_2) + \dots + (\text{eta} * r_N) \tag{7}$$

$$L(y, F(x)) = \sum L(y_i - F(x_i))^2 \tag{8}$$

The next step is to establish the experimentation set-up, after which the Gradient Boosting classifier is applied to the real-time dataset, and the metric values are derived from the performance of the model. In addition to that, it is represented as a graph in figure 6.

Figure 6– Results of Gradient Boosting Classifier

4.3 XGB Classifier

It is an effective implementation of the gradient boosting method that is known as XGBoost. Designed to be very efficient and scalable, it is able to easily manage enormous datasets and is designed to be highly

efficient. For the purpose of training the XGB classifier, the following formula is utilized:

$$F_0(x) = \operatorname{argmin}_y \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, \gamma) \tag{9}$$

$$f(x) = a_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(a_n \cos \frac{n\pi x}{L} + b_n \sin \frac{n\pi x}{L} \right) \tag{10}$$

The loss function is given as

$$rm = -\alpha \left[\delta \left(\frac{L(y, F(x))}{F(x)} \right) \right] \text{ for all } F(x) = F_m - 1(x)', \text{ where } \alpha \text{ is the learning rate} \tag{11}$$

The multiplicative factor to boost the model is given as,

$$F_m(x) = F_m - 1(x) + \gamma_m h_m(x) \tag{12}$$

Then the XGBoost classifier is applied on the same benchmark dataset and the model's performance was derived in terms of the metrics as shown in figure 7

Figure 7 – Results of XGB Classifier

4.4 Decision Tree Classifier:

Decision Tree is a simple yet powerful algorithm for classification and regression problems. It creates a tree structure to represent the decisions and the possible outcomes of those decisions. The final predictions are made by traversing the tree from the root to a leaf node.

The decision tree classifier is trained using the following formula:

$$\text{Information Gain} = E_{\text{parent}} - E_{\text{children}} \tag{13}$$

$$\text{Gini Impurity} = 1 - \sum_{j=1}^m P_j^2 \tag{14}$$

$$\text{Entropy} = - \sum p_i \log_2(p_i) \tag{15}$$

Then, the experimentation using decision tree classifier was conducted and the results are plotted as graph as given in figure 8.

Figure 8 – Sample dataset with Decision Tree Classifier Results

4.5 Logistic Regression:

Logistic Regression is a statistical method for classification problems. It uses the logistic function to model the probability of the outcome belonging to a particular class.

The logistic regression classifier is trained using the following formula:

$$P(y=1|x) = 1 / (1 + e^{-(w^T x - b)}) \tag{16}$$

The outcome of this classifier is evaluated using various metrics and is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 – Sample dataset with Logistic Regression Classifier Results

4.6 K-Nearest Neighbors Classifier:

When it comes to classification and regression issues, the K-Nearest Neighbors technique is a straightforward yet effective solution. It locates the k data points that are closest to a new data point and assigns the class based on the class that is the most prevalent among the k data points that are closest to the new data point.

For the purpose of training the K-Nearest Neighbors classifier, the following formula is utilized:

$$D = \{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\} \tag{17}$$

Using the experimentation setup, the graph is drawn and is shown in figure 10.

Figure 10 –Results of K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) Classifier

4.7 Support Vector Classifier (SVC):

One of the most effective algorithms for solving classification issues is called the Support Vector Classifier. It determines the most effective boundary that can be used to divide the various classes.

For the purpose of training the SVC classifier, the following formula is utilized:

$$\text{minimize } w, b, \xi \left(\frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum \xi_i \right) \tag{18}$$

$$\text{subject to } y_i(w \cdot x_i + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \xi_i \geq 0 \tag{19}$$

The evaluation results of all the metric values are indicated in figure 11.

Figure 11 – Results of Support Vector Machine (SVM) Classifier

4.8 Gaussian Naive Bayes:

When it comes to classification issues, the Gaussian Naive Bayes method provides a straightforward yet effective solution. The assumption that the features are independent and Gaussian distributed is the foundation upon which it is carried out.

For the purpose of training the Gaussian Naive Bayes classifier, the following formula is utilized:

$$P(C|X) = P(X|C) * P(C) / P(X) \tag{20}$$

The collected real time data is used as the training and testing data set and the results are drawn using figure 12.

Figure 12 – Sample dataset with Gaussian Naives Bayes Classifier Results

4.9 Bagging Classifier:

One example of an ensemble method for solving classification problems is the Bagging Classifier. An example of this would be a collection of base classifiers, each of which is trained on a different subset of the training data. Averaging the predictions provided by each classifier is the method that is used to arrive at the final predictions.

The following formula is utilized in the training process of the Bagging classifier:
 BaggingClassifier (base_estimator=None, n_estimators=10, max_samples=1.0, max_features=1.0, bootstrap=True, bootstrap_features=False, oob_score=False, warm_start=False, n_jobs=None, random_state=None, verbose=0)

The results of this classifier are indicated in figure 13.

Figure 13 –Results of Bagging Classifier

4.10 AdaBoost Classifier:

In the context of classification problems, the AdaBoost Classifier is an ensemble method application. The collection is comprised of a number of weak classifiers, each of which is trained on the same dataset, but with varying weights applied to the instances that are used for training. It is through the process of merging the predictions of each classifier that the final predictions are manufactured. By applying the following formula, the AdaBoost classifier is trained:

AdaBoostClassifier (base_estimator=None, n_estimators=50, learning_rate=1.0, algorithm='SAMME.R', random_state=None)

The results are given in figure 14.

Figure 14 –Ada Boost Classifier Results

4.11 Voting Classifier:

Voting Classifier is an ensemble method for classification problems. It combines the predictions of multiple classifiers and assigns the class based on the majority vote. The Voting classifier is trained using the following formula:

`VotingClassifier(estimators, voting='hard' or 'soft', n_jobs=None, weights=None)`

The evaluation results of the voting classifier are displayed in figure 15.

Figure 15 –Voting Classifier Results

4.12 Results using Ensemble Learning

For the dataset taken for analysis, Gradient Boosting based ML model was applied as it has higher accuracy and F1 Score. The proposed work used this classifier as the base model and the proposed work applied the soft voting method to get better prediction results. The dataset is now taken to apply the soft voting classifier as it has produced good results among other ensemble classifiers and provided as a unified method. The final ensemble classifier built has provided higher accuracy when compared to all the other models.

The results of each feature in classification are indicated in the following plots given in Figure 16.

Figure 16 – Features classification using Ensemble Learning

From the above plots, it is identified that, the proposed ensemble learning based classification helps to predict the parameters which are the reasons for diabetics. Hence, the critical symptoms causing parameters are classified and provided for further attention to cure the patients.

The evaluation metrics from this ensemble based work are derived and the plot as in figure 17.

Figure 17 – Proposed Ensemble Learning Metric Values

Also, from the graph plotted in Figure 16 indicates that, the proposed ensemble learning based classifier produced improved accuracy than other ML classifiers.

4.13 SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

To do the analysis, the algorithms are coded in Python with the different datasets related to diabetics. Based on the implementation, the proposed ensemble learning framework has provided higher level of accuracy in predicting the diabetics causing parameters by classifying the critical and non-critical symptoms associated with the patients. The proposed work has yielded an accuracy of 91.02% with epochs of 500. If the other hyper parameters values are updated from the default values, the accuracy can be increased however time taken will be higher. Based on the criticality and accuracy, the above rate is achieved as the non-loss based one.

5. Comparative Analysis

In this research, to have a comparative analysis with all the classifiers, the accuracy, precision, recall and F1-Score are calculated and the results are given in Table 2.

Table 2 – Various Measures using the existing classifiers

Classifier	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1Score
Random Forest	0.8385	0.7375	0.855	0.79191523
Gradient Boosting	0.875	0.8082	0.8551	0.83098878
XGB Classifier	0.8489	0.7632	0.8405	0.79998703
Decision Tree Classifier	0.8028	0.6781	0.855	0.75634401
Logistic Regression	0.75	0.6153	0.8115	0.69991022
K Nearest Neighbors (KNN)	0.75	0.6265	0.7536	0.68419738
SVC	0.8125	0.6896	0.8695	0.76917093
Gaussian NB	0.75	0.6206	0.7826	0.69224852
Bagging	0.8333	0.7402	0.826	0.78074984
Ada Boost	0.8333	0.7341	0.8405	0.78370513
Voting	0.8645	0.7866	0.855	0.819375
Proposed Ensemble Model	0.9102	0.9100	0.9101	0.91005

The classifiers and their derived metric values are shown in Figures 18(a) to 18(d).

Figure 18(a) – Classifiers Vs. Accuracy

Figure 18(b) - Classifiers Vs.Precision

Figure 18(c) - Classifiers Vs. Recall

Figure 18(d) – Classifiers Vs. F1Score

From the figures 18(a) to 18(d), it is understood that, the proposed ensemble model outperforms the other classifiers. Hence, this research work has provided an insight on the application of ensemble classifier rather

than individual voting and boosting classifiers. The outcomes of this research work are: (i) a unified framework using ensemble learning is proposed and implemented (ii) the comparative analysis of the proposed ensemble learning classifier and other classifiers are meticulously done with various case study datasets and found that, the proposed ensemble classifier outperforms the other classifiers.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Developing a unified framework for real time domain such as healthcare is a real challenging task, In ensemble learning or ensemble model, the prediction of different models are combined to make a final prediction model. Here, it is achieved by means of averaging and voting which is together called as ‘average voting’ which is found to be better than independent learning algorithms. Based on the conducted surveys on the existing works, it is identified that, majority of the applications are relying on Random Forest classifier as a single best classifier. However, when compared with the existing classifiers, the proposed ensemble learning based method has produced better results.

The proposed ensemble learning based algorithm was implemented using Python and the results are found to be promising for future research work. The application of soft voting approach has lessened the amplitude of fluctuations in a learning procedure. Due to this, the over fitting and inaccurate generalization to new datasets are reduced, which is especially helpful with high-dimensional data where missing values can lead to higher variance.

As a future research work, the other combination of classifiers are going to be applied and the crowd sourcing based methods will be examined for the prediction efficiency. Also, in the future research work, the authors have focused on direct real time data collection from a patient through the IoT devices and finding out the accuracy of the proposed unified framework and other traditional and existing classifiers for a real time comparative analysis to produce a solid foundation for further research in this area.

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